

Adoption of Integrated Pest Management Practices among Cocoa Farmers in Ondo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study was on the adoption of Integrated Pest Management (IPM) Practices among Cocoa Farmers in Owo Local Government Area, Ondo State, Nigeria. Specifically the study aimed at ascertain the socio-economic characteristics of the respondents in the study area, assess the level of awareness of integrated pest management practices available to the respondents, examine the factors influencing the decision-making process of the respondents in adopting the practices and identify the constraints faced by cocoa farmers in implementing IPM. Primary data were collected by administering a well-structured questionnaire consisting of closed and open-ended questions. Multistage sampling was employed in the study for the selection of 100 cocoa farmers in the study area. Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The results showed that majority (84%) of the farmers were male, the mean age of the respondents was 47 years with an average household size of 7 members. The major educational qualification of the respondents was secondary school (47%). Ninety-four percent of the respondents practiced Integrated Pest Management (IPM). From the study, the majority (78%) of the respondents attested that the major factor that influenced the decisions of the respondents was training and education. The results further revealed the major benefits of IPM as the increase in cocoa yield, reduction in pest damage, and improvement in cocoa bean quality. Additionally, there was no significant relationship between the socio-economic characteristics and the adoption of IPM. The study recommends that government and agricultural agencies should establish comprehensive training programs focusing on simplifying IPM practices and providing hands-on training. Also provision of affordable credit facilities and subsidies to cocoa farmers to alleviate the high cost of implementing IPM practices.

Keywords: Adoption, Integrated Pest Management, Cocoa farmers

INTRODUCTION

Cocoa cultivation is not only a significant agricultural activity but also an area of intense research due to its nutritional properties and economic importance. Studies have highlighted the health benefits of cocoa consumption, including its potential cardiovascular, cognitive, and metabolic effects (Davison *et al.*, 2020; Ding *et al.*, 2019; Hamedifard *et al.*, 2022; Lampport *et al.*, 2021; Mastroiacovo *et al.*, 2019). However, cocoa, derived from the seeds of *Theobroma cacao*, holds significant economic and nutritional value. Extensive research conducted since 2019 has elucidated various aspects of cocoa, ranging from its phytochemical composition to its potential health benefits (Ding *et al.*, 2019; Mastroiacovo *et al.*, 2019; Davison *et al.*, 2020; Lampport *et al.*, 2021; Hamedifard *et al.*, 2022;). Cocoa is renowned for its high content of flavonoids, particularly flavanols,

which exhibit antioxidant properties and have been associated with cardiovascular health benefits such as improved endothelial function and blood pressure regulation. Additionally, cocoa consumption has shown promise in enhancing cognitive function and mood regulation, as well as improving metabolic health by positively influencing insulin sensitivity and lipid profiles.

Despite its nutritional and economic significance, cocoa cultivation faces challenges from pests and diseases, which can severely impact productivity and quality. Integrated Pest Management (IPM) offers a sustainable approach to pest control in cocoa farming by integrating various control tactics, including cultural, biological, mechanical, and chemical methods. IPM strategies tailored to cocoa cultivation aim to mitigate pest damage while minimizing environmental impacts and ensuring the safety of cocoa products. Therefore, this study focused on the factors influencing the adoption of IPM practices among cocoa farmers. Economic factors, such as cost-effectiveness and access to financial resources, play a crucial role in farmers' decisions to adopt IPM (Dhara *et al.*, 2021). Knowledge and awareness about pests, beneficial organisms, and ecological processes are essential for effective IPM implementation (Gautam *et al.*, 2020). Technological innovations, including remote sensing and decision support tools, enhance the precision and efficiency of IPM practices (Bengochea-Guevara *et al.*, 2019). Policy and institutional support, along with social and cultural factors, also influence the adoption of IPM among cocoa farmers (Hussain *et al.*, 2020; Vanlauwe *et al.*, 2020). Understanding these factors is essential for promoting the widespread adoption of IPM practices and ensuring the sustainability of cocoa production. By addressing barriers to adoption and facilitating the integration of IPM into cocoa farming systems, stakeholders can enhance pest management practices, improve cocoa yields and quality, and contribute to the long-term viability of cocoa cultivation. However, this research work fills the huge knowledge gap by analyzing the adoption of IPM among cocoa farmers in the study area. Specifically, this study intends to:

- ascertain the socio-economic characteristics of the respondents in the study area.
- assess the level of awareness of integrated pest management practices available to the respondents.
- examine the factors influencing the decision-making process of the respondents in adopting the practices.
- identify the constraints faced by cocoa farmers in implementing IPM.

The null hypothesis for the study stated that there was no significant relationship between the socioeconomic characteristics of the farmers and adoption of Integrated Pest Management (IPM) in the study area.

METHODOLOGY

This study was carried out in Owo Local Government Area (LGA) in Ondo State, Southwest of Nigeria. Cocoa farming, in particular, plays a crucial role in the local economy, providing livelihoods for a significant portion of the population. Other agricultural activities in the area include palm oil production, yam cultivation, and poultry farming. The primary data employed in this study were obtained with the aid of a well-structured questionnaire. Multi-stage sampling technique was used to select 100 respondents in this study. In the first stage, five communities were randomly selected and 20 respondents were also randomly selected from each community. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used for the analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socioeconomic Characteristics of the Respondents in the study area

The result from the data analyzed showed the mean age of the respondents to be 47 years. This implies that most of the cocoa farmers in the study area were in the middle age class., between 45 and 54 years of age, representing 37% of the population. The finding of this study corroborates the report that the majority (78.5%) of cocoa farmers in Osun State, Nigeria were above 40 years (Faloni *et al.*, 2022). Greater proportions (84%) of the farmers were males while about 16% were females. This implies that most of the cocoa farmers in the study

area were predominantly male, which confirms the findings of the findings of Akinwalere *et al* 2024 that farm work is skewed towards men because of gender inequalities.

The results further revealed that a greater proportion (90%) of the respondents were married, indicating that most farmers in the study area had dependents, and this could boost productivity thereby increasing their earnings. On the other hand, approximately 6% were widowed, 3% were divorced and 1% were single. The dominant religion among the respondents was Christianity as seen in Table 1 below. However, about 47% of them completed secondary school, indicating that most of the cocoa farmers are moderately literate and will be able to practice Integrated Pest Management (IPM).

The mean household size was 7 persons. The finding implies that farmers in the area had a fairly large household size which is expected to increase their access to farm labour. This finding supports the result of the assertion of Akinwalere, (2019) that relatively large household size enhances the availability of family labor which reduces labor costs in agricultural production. In addition, the results showed that 98% of farmers had a farm size between 0.0-9.9 hectares. This finding could be attributed to the fact that small-scale farming largely dominates the agricultural sector in Nigeria. Also, the findings show that 74% of the farmers had an annual income between one to thirty million naira, implying that the cocoa farmers in the study area are financially buoyant while approximately 71% of the farmers had an annual expenditure between one to five million naira.

Table 1: Respondents Socio-Economic Characteristics in the study areas

Variables	F	%	Mean
Age (Years)			
25-34	10	10.0	
35-44	30	30.0	
45-54	37	37.0	47
55-64	13	13.0	
65-74	9	9.0	
75-84	1	1.0	
Sex			
Male	84	84.0	
Female	16	16.0	
Marital status			
Single	1	1.0	
Married	90	90.0	
Divorced	3	3.0	
Widow/Widower	6	6.0	
Religion			
Christianity	72	72.0	
Islam	21	21.0	
Traditional	7	7.0	
Level of education			
No formal education	1	1.0	
Adult education	1	1.0	
Attempted Primary school	2	2.0	
Completed primary school	22	22.0	
Attempted secondary school	1	1.0	
Completed Secondary school	47	47.0	
Attempted tertiary institution	3	3.0	
Completed tertiary institution	23	23.0	
Household Size			
0-4	26	26.0	
5-9	58	58.0	7.0
10-14	15	15.0	
15-19	0.0	0.0	
20-24	1	1.0	
Farm Size (Hectares)			
0.0-9.9	98	98.0	3.1
10.0-19.9	1	1.0	
20.0-29.9	1	1.0	
Annual income(Naira)			
1-30000000	74	74.0	26010160.00
30000001-60000000	15	15.0	
60000001-90000000	9	9.0	
90000001-120000000	1	1.0	
120000001-150000000	1	1.0	
Annual expenditure (Naira)			
1-5000000	71	71.0	4330175.00
5000000-10000000	22	22.0	
10000001-15000000	6	6.0	
15000001-20000000	1	1.0	

Source: Field Survey 2024

Level of Awareness of Cocoa Farmers of Integrated Pest Management (IPM)

The result of the farmer’s distribution based on the level of awareness of cocoa farmers about IPM is presented in Table 2. It shows that a greater proportion (94%) of the farmers were aware of the practices which may be due to governments, NGOs, and agricultural organizations conducting awareness campaigns and training programs on IPM, leading to a higher level of knowledge among farmers and agricultural stakeholders. 67% of the farmers understood integrated pest management as sole reliance on chemical pesticides; this may be because farmers might not fully comprehend the full concept and approach of IPM, which combines physical, cultural, biological, and chemical controls of pests.

Furthermore, the results revealed that 73% of the respondents first learned about IPM from their fellow farmers, which could result from social networks among farmers, especially in rural areas which makes farmers easily accessible to each other. 63% of the farmers learned about IPM for the first time from workshops/training while 61% of the respondents learned about IPM from extension services; this may have resulted from several trainings and workshops organized by extension workers in the study area.

Table 2: Level of Awareness of the Farmers about Integrated Pest Management (IPM)

	YES F (%)	NO F (%)
Have you heard of Integrated Pest Management (IPM) for cocoa farming?	94	6
What is your understanding of Integrated Pest Management?	(91.0)	(9.0)
Sole reliance on chemical pesticides	67 (67.0)	33 (33.0)
Use of resistant crop varieties	35 (35.0)	65 (65.0)
Avoiding pest monitoring	63 (63.0)	37 (37.0)
Planting shade trees	66 (66.0)	34 (34.0)
How did you first learn about IPM?		
Extension services	61 (61.0)	39 (39.0)
Fellow farmers	73 (73.0)	27 (27.0)
Workshops/training	63 (63.0)	37 (37.0)
Media (radio, TV, internet)	21 (21.0)	97 (97.0)

Source: Field Survey 2024

Respondents Practicing Integrated Pest Management (IPM) in the study area.

The result of the farmers' distribution is presented in Table 3, showing 89% of the farmers practicing IPM, depending on their adopter categories (innovators, early adopters, early majority, late majority, and laggards). This implies that IPM adoption is high among farmers, but there is room for improvement in reducing chemical pesticide reliance. Furthermore, the results in the table showed that the average number of years of practicing IPM by the respondents was 7 years which implies that a significant proportion of the respondents have been practicing IPM over a long period. However, majority (90%) of the respondents in the study area rely only on chemical pesticides to control pests while the remaining do not. Likewise, the farmers recognize IPM's environmental benefits and potential for natural pest control. The finding supports this finding that states that IPM adoption can lead to reduced chemical pesticide use and environmental protection (IFAD) (2020).

Table 3: Result of Respondents Practicing IPM in the study Area.

	YES F (%)	NO F (%)	
Are you practicing any Integrated Pest Management (IPM)?	94 (94.0)	6 (6.0)	
How long have you been practicing any of these Techniques?	F	(%)	Mean
0-4	31	31.0	
5-9	46	46.0	7.11
10-14	12	12.0	
15-19	7	7.0	
20-24	2	2.0	
25-29	1	1.0	
30-34	1	1.0	
	TRUE F (%)	FALSE F (%)	
Integrated pest management (IPM) relies solely on chemical pesticides to control pests	90 (90.0)	10 (10.0)	
IPM encourages using natural methods to control pests whenever possible	83 (83.0)	17 (17.0)	
IPM helps to protect the environment from harmful chemicals	82 (82.0)	18 (18.0)	

Source: Field survey, 2024

Factors influencing the decision of the Cocoa Farmers in adopting IPM in the study area.

The result showing the several factors influencing the decision-making process of the cocoa farmers in adopting IPM is presented in Table 4. Majority (78%) of the respondents who practiced IPM affirmed that training and education were a major factor influencing their decisions to adopt IPM practices. Likewise, some believed that peer influence (49%), extension services (46%), cost of implementation (37%), availability of resources (34%), and environmental impacts (14%) influence their decisions to adopt IPM practices in the study area. This result implies that most of the respondents had been exposed to a great deal of training and education and this may have been because of consequent training and visits by extension workers to the area as supported by Akinwalere, *et al.* (2019a). The finding aligns with the existing study that revealed that peer influences and support from extension services significantly influence farmers' adoption of IPM practices. (IITA (2020). Table 4 also shows that the non-adopting farmers utilize several methods (such as biotechnology methods (GMOs), crop rotation and proper spacing, heavy use of chemicals, organic farming, crop rotation, and so many others) on their cocoa farm.

Factors Influencing the Adoption of Integrated Pest Management by the respondents in the study area

The results in Table 5 further revealed several factors influencing the adoption of IPM by the cocoa farmers in the study area. The mean scores on the table were used to show the degree to which the factors influence the adoption of IPM by the respondents as reported by them. Therefore, the most influencing factors were complications in the implementation of the IPM practices ($\bar{x}=2.79.$), the provision of adequate support from the government and agricultural extension services ($\bar{x}=2.30.$), and the high cost of IPM practices than traditional

pest management by the farmers ($\bar{x}=2.22$). The least factors that influence the adoption of IPM practices were reported by the respondents as the benefits of IPM practices than traditional pest management by the farmers ($\bar{x}=2.22$). The least factors that influence the adoption of IPM practices were reported by the respondents as the benefits of IPM practices for long-term pest management ($\bar{x}=1.66$) and the use of the IPM practices to increase cocoa yield.

Table 5: Factors Influencing the Adoption of Integrated Pest Management (IPM) by Cocoa Farmers in the study area.

Factors	Strongly agree. (F) (%)	Agree (F) (%)	Disagree (F) (%)	Strongly disagree. (F) (%)	Mean
IPM practices are too complicated to implement.	12 (12.0)	19 (19.0)	47 (47.0)	22 (22.0)	2.79
Government and agricultural extension services provide adequate support for adopting IPM practices.	27 (27.0)	31 (31.0)	27 (27.0)	15 (15.0)	2.30
IPM practices are more expensive than traditional pest control methods.	20 (20.0)	52 (52.0)	14 (14.0)	14 (14.0)	2.22
IPM practices are beneficial for long-term pest management.	55 (55.0)	32 (32.0)	5 (5.0)	8 (8.0)	1.66
Using IPM practices can increase cocoa yield.	66 (66.0)	24 (24.0)	1 (1.0)	9 (9.0)	1.53

Source: Field Survey 2024

Perceived Benefits in adopting IPM Practices by the respondents in the study area.

Findings as shown in table 6 revealed the perceived benefit of adopting IPM practices by the respondents. The most perceived benefit is increase cocoa yield (84%), reduction in pest damage (76%), improvement in cocoa bean quality (68%) and reduction in reliance on chemical pesticides (64%). These benefits suggest that farmers perceive IPM as an effective way to boost their cocoa production, minimize crop losses, enhance quality, and reduce harmful chemical use. However, there is a relatively low percentage of farmers recognizing environmental protection as a benefit (13%) which indicates a limited understanding of IPM's broader ecological advantages. This limited awareness may be due to a lack of exposure to environmental education or training, insufficient information on IPM's environmental benefits, or a primary focus on economic benefits rather than environmental concerns. The low recognition of environmental benefits also implies that farmers may not fully comprehend the long-term consequences of chemical pesticide use on their ecosystems, such as soil degradation, water pollution, and loss of biodiversity. Overall, the findings highlight the need for education and awareness programs to promote IPM's environmental benefits and encourage sustainable cocoa production practices among farmers in the study area. This will help bridge the knowledge gap and foster a more holistic understanding of IPM's advantages

Table 6: Perceived Benefits of IPM Practices by Cocoa Farmers in the study area.

Perceived Benefits	YES F (%)	NO F (%)
Increase cocoa yield	84 (84.0)	16 (16.0)
Improve cocoa bean quality	68 (68.0)	32 (32.0)

Reduce pest damage	76 (76.0)	24 (24.0)
Protect the environment	31 (31.0)	69 (69.0)
Reduce reliance on chemical pesticides	64 (64.0)	38 (36.0)

Source: Field Survey 2024

Constraints Faced in Implementing IPM by the respondents in the study area

Table 7 shows the various constraints faced by the respondents in implementing IPM in the study area. The respondents reported that there were three major constraints they faced while implementing IPM and they included resistance from pests ($\bar{x}=2.36.$), complexity of practices ($\bar{x}=2.27.$), and high cost ($\bar{x}=2.24.$). This indicates that the constraints existed because IPM requires specialized knowledge and skills to be effectively implemented. On the other hand, the less prevailing constraints were labor constraints ($\bar{x}=2.18.$), limited availability of resources ($\bar{x}=2.17.$), lack of support from extension services ($\bar{x}=2.08.$), and lack of knowledge or training ($\bar{x}=1.99.$). However, the implication of this finding if left unaddressed is that it may lead to continued reliance on chemical pesticides, exacerbating environmental degradation and health risks, decreased cocoa yields and quality, affecting farmers' livelihoods and national economy, and limited adoption of climate-resilient agricultural practices, increasing vulnerability to climate change

Table 7: Constraints faced in implementing Integrated Pest Management (IPM) by the respondents in the study area.

Constraints	Major constraint F (%)	Minor constraint F (%)	Not a constraint F (%)	Mean
Resistance from pests	11 (11.0)	42 (42.0)	47 (47.0)	2.36
Complexity of practices	14 (14.0)	45 (45.0)	41 (41.0)	2.27
High cost	17 (17.0)	42 (42.0)	41 (41.0)	2.24
Labor constraints	21 (21.0)	40 (40.0)	39 (39.0)	2.18
Limited availability of resources	20 (20.0)	43 (43.0)	37 (37.0)	2.17
Lack of support from extension services	19 (19.0)	54 (54.0)	27 (27.0)	2.08
Lack of knowledge/training	26 (26.0)	49 (49.0)	25 (25)	1.99

Source: Field Survey 2024

Relationship between the Socio-economic characteristics of the respondents and adoption of Integrated Pest Management (IPM) Practices.

Table 8 reveals the findings shows that there is no significant relationship between the socioeconomic

characteristics of the respondents and the adoption of IPM practices. This implies that none of these socio-economic characteristics significantly determine the adoption of IPM practices among cocoa farmers in the study area. The lack of significant relationships suggests that socio-economic characteristics alone may not be reliable predictors of IPM adoption. This indicates that other factors, such as awareness campaigns, access to agricultural extension services, education, or economic incentives, might play a more substantial role. Therefore, efforts to promote IPM practices should focus on interventions unrelated to the demographic or socio-economic profiles of farmers. For instance, training programs, subsidies, or practical demonstrations might prove more effective than tailoring strategies based on age, gender, or farm size.

Table 8: Relationship Between the Socio-Economic Characteristics of Respondents and adoption of Integrated Pest Management (IPM) Practices

Variables	p-values	r
Age	0.408	0.084
Sex	0.701	-0.039
Religion	0.663	0.044
Marital status	0.221	0.123
Farm size	0.989	-0.001

Source: Field survey, 2024

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study revealed that majority of the cocoa farmers adopted Integrated Pest Management (IPM) practices in the study area. They recognized the value of IPM and are willing to adopt these practices. To enhance adoption rates and effectiveness, it is crucial to simplify IPM practices, provide adequate training, offer financial supports and resources, strengthen extension services and programs, and promote peer-to-peer learning and knowledge sharing. The findings provide valuable insights for policymakers, extension agents, and other stakeholders seeking to promote sustainable agricultural practices in Nigeria. Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

- Policymakers and stakeholders should develop and implement policies that promote sustainable cocoa production, including incentives for farmers who adopt IPM practices, regulations on chemical pesticide use, and support for organic farming initiatives.
- Agricultural extension services should be strengthened to provide regular support and guidance to cocoa farmers on IPM practices.
- Financial institutions and government agencies should provide affordable credit facilities and subsidies to cocoa farmers to alleviate the high cost of implementing IPM practices.
- The government and private sector should promote farmer associations and cooperatives to foster collective action and support, peer-to-peer learning, and knowledge sharing among cocoa farmers through farmer field schools, workshops, and demonstration plots.
- The government and agricultural agencies should establish comprehensive training programs for cocoa farmers, focusing on simplifying IPM practices and providing hands-on training.

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Result

The result showing the several factors influencing the decision-making process of the cocoa farmers in the study area in adopting IPM is presented in Table 4. Majority (78%) of the respondents who practiced IPM affirmed that training and education were a major factor influencing their decisions to adopt IPM practices. Likewise, some believed that peer influence (49%), extension services (46%), cost of implementation (37%), availability of resources (34%), and environmental impacts (14%) influence their decisions to adopt IPM practices in the study area. This result implies that most of the respondents had been exposed to a great deal of training and education and this may have been because of consequent training and visits by extension workers to the area as supported by Akinwalere, *et al.* (2019a). The finding aligns with the existing study that revealed that peer influences and support from extension services significantly influence farmers' adoption of IPM practices. (IITA, 2020). Table 4 also shows that the non-adopting farmers utilize several methods (such as biotechnology methods (GMOs), crop rotation and proper spacing, heavy use of chemicals, organic farming, crop rotation, and so many others) on their cocoa farms.

Table 4: Factors Influencing the Decision of the Respondents in Adopting Integrated Pest Management (IPM) in the study area.

Factors influencing the decision to adopt IPM practices	YES F (%)	NO F (%)
Cost of implementation	37 (37.0)	63 (63.0)
Availability of resources	34 (34.0)	66 (66.0)
Training and Education	78 (78.0)	22 (22.0)
Support from extension services	46 (46.0)	54 (54.0)
Peer influence	49 (49.0)	51 (51.0)
Environmental impact	14 (14.0)	86 (86.0)

Source: Field Survey 2024